

WOMEN ATTAIN IDENTITY AND SELF IN TONI MORRISON NOVEL MERCY AND PARADISE

P. Deepa,

Research Scholar,

Department of English, SCSVMV (Deemed to be University),
Enathur, Kancheepuram-631561.

Dr. Venkatraman,

Former Professor of English,

SCSVMV (Deemed to be University), Enathur, Kancheepuram-631561.

Abstract

Toni Morrison is among the pioneer of those contemporary black women writers, best known for her intricately woven novels. She delves in the lives of African American women, and examining how they face a predicament situation in patriarchal society. Furthermore, women experience similar stage in their struggles like: haunting memories, the fear of abandonment and sexual relationship. After facing the predicament situation, certain women try to uplift from their oppression and attain identity and self in the progress of the novel A Mercy and Paradise. In this article we will attempt to demonstrate that both novels, women characters somehow manage to redefine themselves by coming to terms with their pasts. Infact they manage to reach the psychological development to attain their space in this unjust society.

Keywords: literary darkness, community, psychological development and self-identity.

Chloe Anthony Wofford (born 1931), famously known as Toni Morrison choosing the lives of African Americans as the main subject of her literary discourse. She lifts the black man and woman out of the “literary darkness”, thus breaking with earlier author’s stereotypical portrayal of African Americans. Morrison is an excellent storyteller, who makes the reader participate in the novel to create meaning. Morrison incredible string of lyrical, adventurous modern classics, vividness, immediacy of characters, imaginative and talent of describing the experience as ideas, all these makes her novel so powerful and claim her position as one of America’s best novelists. Morrison’s depiction of black women’s sexuality is often unconventional and aims to deconstruct the stereotypes of black

female characters, especially in the women-centered novels.¹ African American women are bound together in the ethnic heritage and their bonds run deep, beyond biological and spousal relationships. Morrison gave importance to African ancestor in her work. They help abandoned characters and guide them to rise above the circumstances in which they find themselves low and critical. Ancestors interact with characters as collective history or through ancestral stories. She forces the reader's memory because of her belief that reconstructive memory, is a necessary basis for constructing the future. Demanding respect for women in the male – dominated black community and strive for the black woman as an integral part of the black community and also asking recognition of their achievements and contributions. Morrison uses writing to explore the aspects of black life connected to race, class, gender as well as to explore the relationship between women and voice, through that she give importance to the ancestors and portrays ordinary black girls, women and men.

Identity and Self in *A Mercy*

Morrison powerful, elemental material bears reworking and revisiting in her novel. Her play on sorrow and happiness thematically reflects the instability of the narrative and combines multiple internal focalizations with a narrative that mostly employs variable internal focalizations with fluidity of the characters and the cultures that populate *A Mercy* novel.² *A Mercy* novel setting start from the close of the seventeenth century that is the beginning of slavery in America where race was far more diverse and complex period than is generally imagined today. It is a visceral, intricately textured novel that takes readers right to the origins of America, when race was not yet rhetorically constructed as an absolute category and civil war were already being sown. The action and narrative voice of the story allows the reader to see the history of the character, as well as their present circumstances. Morrison uses multiple narrators with biblical references, history, love which turned inside out, ghost, heart-wrenching tale and folk wisdom. The reader falls under the spell of a narrator, who moving easily from third person to first and cannot rest until her story is told, heard and deeply felt.

Morrison's handling more multifaceted issues in *A Mercy* than in her previous novels. As usual mother and daughter relationship, love, love of all kinds. Slaves are white as well as black,

¹ Pozorski A. L., 2003, Race. – E. A. Beaulieu (ed.), *The Toni Morrison Encyclopaedia*. US: Greenwood Press, 277–285.

² Morrison, Toni. *A Mercy*. London: Random House, 2008.

women of all races are at the mercy of men.³ *A Mercy* spins the tale of an ostensibly abandoned daughter of a young slave girl, named Florens. When Jacob arrives as a trader, he clearly understand the situation in plantation, there is no money to pay him. Senhor frankly admits that he cannot pay the debt; instead he offers one of his slaves as partial payment, fluid currency, and human flesh. When Jacob chooses Florens mother Minha Mae has payment for a bad debt from Senhor. She gives up her daughter on him because the girl is in danger of falling in to worst hands.

Morrison explores and depict sexuality's full spectrum of possibility, its capacity to express love, hate, joy, sadness, compassion and lust. She treats it the same way that she approaches all aspects of human relationships- without sentiment or censure. She uses different aspects of sexuality to show the influence of the social environment on the characters minds, emotions and actions. Florens mother Minha Mae used the first chance she get to free her daughter from the place, although her mother cannot provide protection, she can find a difference. Florens don't know, why her mother choose her brother and prefer to give her to Jacob. Morrison gives voice to Florens mother, Minha Mae the reason why she choose her daughter instead of her son. Minha Mae has the ability to improve her life but she gives up her daughter for a chance. It is out of pure motherly love, she could do best thing to protect her daughter from a life of rape and abuse. Florens mother give her a chance for a better life, although Florens would always think she is abandoned.

Through the character of Florens mother, Morrison use the repetition of 'We' in order to emphasize the condition of black slave women in such a society. Florens mother denies the existed stereotype that other black slave women followed. She denies the image of obedient black female slave by rejecting her daughter, Florens and reveals herself being capable making a strong decision. Through her novel she gave voices to those who not been heard, before voices silenced first by cruelty and then by history. Through an act of mercy, Florens becomes part of the household of the Jacob Vaarks, including other members like Sorrow and Lina. Each of these characters as own voice and story in 'A Mercy'.

Florens, infatuated with the blacksmith, a freed slave. He fall in love with Florens, he wants nothing except her submission. Florens feels possessive in blacksmith, she not able to accept that blacksmith take care and love for boy. After seeing the Florens wilderness, blacksmith reject her.

³ Jennings, La Vinia Delois. "A Mercy: Toni Morrison Plots the Formation of Racial Slavery in Seventeenth-Century America." *Callaloo* 32 (2009): 645-649.

Florens has removed herself from community and perceives herself purely as individual. At last Florens write her own story, carving the letters with a nail into the walls of her dead master's unfinished and abandoned house. In the end of the novel, Florens does not laments, especially after separate from the blacksmith. In order to survive, Morrison's characters need to choose whether to exist in the shadows, submerging their identities, or to fight back, proving that they have a self-worth respecting.⁴ She is no longer boneless woman because now she able to avoid emotional enslavement. This growth she got from experience after losing the blacksmith. Morrison by implementing many perspectives in the novel, she opens the reader's eyes to consider all angles before judging someone. Sorrow, the daughter of a sea captain, found almost dying in a shipwreck, whom like Florens Jacob took pity. Her name 'Sorrow' comes from her tendency to wander, her lack of knowledge and laziness, and her strange, melancholy personality. Sorrow after giving birth to her daughter, feel independence and freedom from her former misery driven self.⁵ Even she convinced 'that she had done something important by herself'.

Sorrow stops wandering after the birth of her child and do organized and routine duties. Childbirth gives her the confidence and she suggest that it empowers the women in general. The birth of the baby makes Sorrow literally and figuratively complete and she emergence as an organized and motivated individual. The black women characters who are raised from their poor, down trodden and most humiliating position to a new sense of awareness of freedom, liberty and equality in their society.

By writing this novel, Toni Morrison is using her own voice. She adds it to the voices of African-American women before her, joining the mothers humming lullabies, the field hands with their subversive chants, the blues singers, the gospel choirs, the poets and writers and storytellers. Through their expression, these women chronicle a history not only for themselves but for their culture. Most of the women depending on men for a sense of self, but some women are able to regain their voices as the novel progresses. It adds authenticity and credibility to Morrison's voice. Her fiction depict a variety of family structures, because she insists the importance of family for African American. Family provides individuals with a sense of identity, community and history.

⁴ Boyce Davies, Carole. *Black Women, Writing and Identity: Migrations of the Subject*. New York: Routledge, 1994.

⁵ Davis, Cynthia A. "Self, Society, and Myth in Toni Morrison's Fiction" *Toni Morrison: Contemporary Critical Essay*. Ed. Linden Peach. U.S.A: Macmillan Press, 1988: 27-42.

Slavery separated families deliberately and capriciously. Another slave women in Jacob house is Lina. Lina is free to decide and act anything she likes, but in the end of the novel only. In the beginning she also suffers lot. When Florens arrived at Jacob house, she immediately ‘falls in love with her’ and takes Florens to be her daughter and thus makes herself a mother. Lina immediately recognizes the threat to Florens innocence, when the blacksmith arrives at Jacob house. Torn between her motherly concern for Florens and Rebekka, she decide to sacrifices Florens by sending her to find the blacksmith. Lina thought this is the only way to save Rebekka. Thus, Lina had to become her own woman and primed herself to be a mother to others by mothering herself. Lina, through her identification with nature and Sorrow, through motherhood, are able to overcome their orphaned status. Florens, makes a spiritual journey to identity that is empowering and liberating.

Identity and Self in Paradise

Paradise novel, exposes a violence directed towards women, extreme by murdering five women. It includes people of two communities, all black people in town called Ruby and the women in convent. The main plot deals with a quarrel between these two communities. In *Paradise*, the women of the convent are mainly five members they are Consolata Sosa, Seneca, Mary Magna, Pallas Truelove and Grace Gibson. Their main fall is, they express compassion for others, but an inability to exercise any compassion toward themselves. They are suffered by sexual trespass, violence of abuse, alcoholism and neglect or betrayed by their families.⁶

Ruby town was created by old fathers based on interracial discrimination they faced. Town fathers not allow any outsiders enter in to the Ruby and they prevent change. Anything goes wrong in the town, Ruby men blame the Convent women and leads to tensions. Ruby men attacking the women of convent reflect the nature of men’s dominant position and fear of losing their power over women in society.

Convent is an entirely female environment give shelter to those women who struggle to heal their wounds. Everyone in the convent support each other and nurture. Consolata Sosa was mother figure to the women who gravitate there and support each other in their journeys toward wholeness and independence. The convent is paradise for those women who seeking refuge. Ruby men are disturbed by convent women. Infact their unconventional household and strange behaviour are

⁶ Morrison, Toni. *Paradise*. London: Vintage Books, 1999.

threatening force to the men. The convent is transformed into a safe heaven for not only to wayward women but also to many of Ruby's citizens who visit convent in times of their trouble.

Morrison's always presents the elder characters, one who is not just a parental figure, but a timeless presents. These characters are supposed to protect the younger, instruct them with wisdom, and in turn identity.⁷ In *Paradise* Mary Magna plays a mother role and gave moral support and guide after her death also to Consolata. Consolata acts as a motherly figure to other women in the convent, after the death of Mary Magna. Mary Magna dies and wayward women have started making their home at the Convent. Strong emphasis should be put on the relationships between women, Consolata is passing her own personal experience to the rest of the women. Consolata's successful negotiation of an institutionalized patriarchal ideology, which allows her to become a spiritual healer and guide, without a healer and guide women in convent cannot heal. Consolata starts to leads the women in sessions of 'loud-dreaming' that allow them to exorcise the ghosts that haunt them. She marshals the convent women with clean, shave heads and insists to work together and share their stories made the women into a new sense of purpose in life. Each women at the convent is afforded the chance to heal herself, reclaim her identity, and most of all, love herself, after the assault by men of Ruby.⁸ Each of the women returns to her origins, either to confront the past or to make peace with it and reveal how much they have healed.

Morrison wanted readers to realize that race is the least reliable information for defining or understanding the convent women. So that only Morrison not assign a racial category to the convent women. Morrison not only show the evil and dominant side of white people in the novels but also black people face the oppression from within the community. *Paradise* is good example than any other novel of Morrison that incorporate all types of blackness and realistically portray the positive visions of African American identity.

Morrison fights for a more egalitarian society in *Paradise*. She emphasizes the dynamic nature of the oral tradition, cultural beliefs and values. *Paradise* is also a rich source of oral tradition and explores beliefs about good and evil, supernatural and ancestors that stem from African tradition. Through this she conveys the knowledge that African American have accumulated for how to survive and endure in America. Morrison engages her characters in calling on the wisdom of their African

⁷ Badt, Karin Luisa. "The Roots of the Body in Toni Morrison: A Mater of 'Ancient Properties.'" *African American Review* 29:4 (1995): 567-577.

⁸ Davis, Angela. *Women, Race, and Class*. Reading: Women's Press, 1991.

ancestors to help them meditate and rise above the circumstance in which they find themselves, even if this calling is subconscious or complicated with problems. At the same time she writes about historical and social matters and frequently uses sexuality as a means of making her character portrayals more intensely personal because individual being is always the centre of attention.

Conclusion

Throughout her novels, Morrison demonstrates to the reader that there are many ways to be a family, and shows characters seeking to create some sense of family within their communities. This female protagonists achieve new self-empowerment by create communities that foster a wholeness which transcends class, racial and gender lines encourage women. African American culture, migrations, trips and travels of all sorts pervade the action of Morrison novels and she emphasis the historical elements also. By digging past, her characters probe the depths of African American history and experience through that, she emphasis the individual as always and already part of the community. ⁹Morrison demonstrates that inward exploration often overlaps with exterior travels, resulting in reinventing of oneself. Morrison concepts of literacy, freedom and slavery is not just with in the contest of the African-American experience but explores in every man and woman.

Morrison through her novels reflects values, beliefs, social conditions and mindset of the people with focus on female protagonists. These females achieve their goal by resisting conventional social construction and comprising individual freedom, equality to do to get what they want. These female protagonists empower themselves by literal or psychological journey during which they confronts physical or psychological enslavement so that they may achieve personal freedom.

⁹ Kubitscheck, D. Missy. *Toni Morrison: A Critical Companion*. London: Greenwood Press, 1988.